

8th Brazilian Symposium on Programming Languages

J.UCS Special Issue

Rafael Dueire Lins

(Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Recife, PE, Brazil
rdl@ee.ufpe.br)

This special issue presents a selection of papers presented at SBLP 2004, the 8th Brazilian Symposium on Programming Languages, which took place from 26 to 28 May 2004, in Niterói, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

The opening paper of the issue is an invited contribution by David A. Turner (Middlesex University, England), one of the most important names in the functional programming paradigm, whose seminal contributions span from the design to the implementation of programming languages.

The other papers in this issue were selected out of 53 submissions from all over the world by a program committee of 42 widely acknowledged experts, with the help of 23 other colleagues. The selection of articles in this journal issue gives an interesting overview of current trends in the area of programming languages.

Recife, Brazil
July 2004

Rafael Dueire Lins

Program Committee

- Guido Araújo, UNICAMP (Brazil)
- Luis Soares Barbosa, Univ. do Minho (Portugal)
- Gabriel Baum, Univ. Nacional de La Plata (Argentina)
- Nick Benton, Microsoft Research (England)
- Roberto Bigonha, UFMG (Brazil)
- Mariza Bigonha, UFMG (Brazil)
- Paulo Borba, UFPE (Brazil)
- Christiano Braga, UFF (Brazil)
- Barrett Bryant, Univ. of Alabama at Birmingham (USA)
- Isabel Cafezeiro, UFF (Brazil)
- Carlos Camarão, UFMG (Brazil)
- Francisco Heron de Carvalho Jr., UPE (Brazil)
- Renato Cerqueira, PUC-Rio (Brazil)
- Guy Cousineau, Univ. Paris 7 (France)
- Sergiu Dascalu, Univ. of Nevada, Reno (USA)
- Edil Fernandes, UFRJ (Brazil)

- José Luiz Fiadeiro, Univ. of Leicester (England)
- Lucília Figueiredo, UFOP (Brazil)
- Alex Garcia, IME (Brazil)
- José Guimarães, UFSCAR (Brazil)
- Edward Hermann Hæusler, PUC-Rio (Brazil)
- John Hughes, Chalmers Univ. of Technology (Sweden)
- Roberto Ierusalimschy, PUC-Rio (Brazil)
- Johan Jeuring, Utrecht Univ. (Netherlands)
- José Labra, Univ. of Oviedo (Spain)
- Ricardo Massa Lima, UPE (Brazil)
- Rafael Dueire Lins, UFPE - **Chair** (Brazil)
- Alfio Martini, PUC-RS (Brazil)
- Paulo Blauth Menezes, UFRGS (Brazil)
- Hermano Moura, UFPE (Brazil)
- Martin Musicante, UFPR (Brazil)
- David Naumann, Stevens Tech (USA)
- Catuscia Palamidessi, INRIA Futurs (France)
- Alberto Pardo, Univ. de La Republica (Uruguay)
- Uday Reddy, Univ. of Birmingham (England)
- Noemi Rodriguez, PUC-Rio (Brazil)
- Cecília Rubira, Unicamp (Brazil)
- André Santos, UFPE (Brazil)
- João Saraiva, Univ. do Minho (Portugal)
- Peter Thiemann, Univ. Freiburg (Germany)
- Simon Thompson, Univ. of Kent (England)
- Marco Túlio Valente, PUC-MG (Brazil)